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POWDER MICROSCOPICAL EVALUATION OF INGREDIENTS OF TRIJATAKA

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Abstract

Background: Crude drugs are naturally occurring forms such as plants, animals, and their parts that are only dried, divided into longitudinal or transverse pieces, or peeled after collecting. Over the past three decades, the number of people using natural medications has expanded rapidly to the rate of at least 80% of the global population. They are also highly demanded in the developed world for all medical issues due to their effectiveness, safety, and low occurrence of adverse effects. Despite the fact that there are a number of limitations with herbs, such as adulteration. In that concern evaluation of crude drugs becomes an essential tool for authentication of the plants. This includes reporting substitution and adulteration, identifying deterioration caused by treatment and storage, and determining the biochemical variation in the medications. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Trijataka* was carried out. *Trijataka* is an Ayurvedic formulation containing *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton), *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl), *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.). *Slides* of each ingredient of *Trijataka* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Trijataka* shows pearl gland, glandular trichomes, fibers, vessels, starch grains, pitted vessels, phloem fibers etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The microscopic structures which are observed in *Trijataka* help in the correct identification of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton), *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl), and *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.). Powder microscopy is one of the easiest methods which helps in quality control and assurance of herbal drug.

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INTRODUCTION:

Microscopy is useful for the study of the internal structure, constitution of plant and animal cells or other objects in detail. It is necessary for the detection of adulterants and contaminants of the herbal preparations and thus provides means for assessing the authenticity of herbal drugs. When analyzing crude pharmaceuticals under a microscope, factors such as the form and composition of the cell contents, the size, shape, and relative positions of various cells and tissues are taken into consideration.

Powder microscopy inspection is a crucial step in the identification of medicinal plant materials, especially for detecting broken or powdered components. As a result, powder microscopy is essential for identifying and locating contaminants in herbal medications. Here, for the present study *Trijataka* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Trijataka* is an important polyherbal formulation of the Ayurved.¹ It contains *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton, Family - *Scitaminae*), *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl, Family - *Lauraceae*), and *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm., Family - *Lauraceae*).

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Trijataka*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features in the powder of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton), *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl), and *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.) .
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Trijataka was used for the powder microscopy. *Trijataka* is an Ayurvedic formulation containing *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton), *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl), and *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm. Seeds of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton), stembark of *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl), and leaf of *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.). were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Trijataka* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference²⁻⁴

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No.1: Powder microscopic characters found in *Trijataka*

No.	Microscopic characters	<i>Ela</i>	<i>Twaka</i>	<i>Patra</i>
1.	Prismatic crystals	+		
2.	Parenchymatous cell	+		
3.	Fiber	+		+

4.	Epidermal cells	+		
5.	Acicular crystal	+		
6.	Starch grains	+	+	
7.	Sclerenchyma of testa	+		
8.	Pitted vessel		+	
9.	Phloem Fiber		+	
10.	Phloem parenchyma		+	
11.	Parenchyma containing small acicular raphides		+	
12.	Scleroids		+	
13.	Pearl gland			+
14.	Thick-walled cell of upper epidermis			+
15.	Vessel			+
16.	Schizogenous mucilaginous canal			+
17.	Glandular Trichomes			+
18.	Non-glandular Trichomes			+

Table No.2: Powder microscopic study of *Ela (Elettaria cardemomum (Linn.) Maton)*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Ela</i>	Figure no.
1.	Prismatic crystals	01
2.	Parenchymatous cell	02, 07
3.	Fiber	03
4.	Epidermal cells	04
5.	Acicular crystal	05
6.	Starch grains	06
7.	Sclerenchyma of testa	08

Table No.3: Powder microscopic study of *Patra (Cinamomum tamala (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.)*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Patra</i>	Figure no.
1.	Fiber	09

2.	Pearl gland	10
3.	Thick-walled cell of upper epidermis	11
4.	Vessel	12
5.	Schizogenous mucilaginous canal	13
6.	Glandular Trichomes	14
7.	Non-glandular Trichomes	15
No.	Characteristics of <i>Twaka</i>	Figure no.
1.	Starch grain	16
2.	Pitted vessel	
3.	Phloem Fiber	
4.	Phloem parenchyma	
5.	Parenchyma containing small acicular raphides	
6.	Scleroids	

Table No.4: Powder microscopic study of *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Twaka</i>	Figure no.
1.	Starch grain	16
2.	Pitted vessel	16
3.	Phloem parenchyma	17
4.	Phloem Fiber	18
5.	Parenchyma containing small acicular raphides	19
6.	Scleroids	20

The current study provides knowledge on the microscopic characteristics of the herbal materials. The powder of *Trijataka* was chosen for this microscopic investigation. Powder microscopy of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton) shows, prismatic crystals, parenchymatous cell, fiber, epidermal cells, acicular crystal, starch grains, sclerenchyma of testa. Powder microscopy of *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl) shows, starch grain, pitted vessel, phloem fiber, phloem parenchyma, parenchyma containing small acicular raphides, scleroids. Powder microscopy of *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. - Ham.) Nees & Eberm.) shows, fiber, pearl gland, thick-walled cell of upper epidermis, vessel, schizogenous mucilaginous canal, glandular trichomes, non-glandular trichomes.

The process of standardizing Ayurvedic formulation is compound and difficult. However, it is imperative to ensure the efficacy and safety of herbal remedies, making them appropriate for their application. In the current experiment, every powder component of *Trijataka* was inspected under a

microscope and its microscopic properties were noted. These qualities might be helpful in accurately recognizing and detecting impurities in powder.

Powder microscopy of *Elettaria cardemomum*

Powder microscopy of *Cinnamomum Tamala*

Fig.09

Fiber

Fig.10

Pearl gland

Fig.11

Thick-walled cell of upper epidermis

Schizogenous mucilaginous canal

Fig.12

Vessel

Fig.13

Fig.14

Glandular Trichomes

Non-glandular Trichomes

Fig.15

Powder microscopy of *Cinnamomum verum*

Fig.16

Fig.17

Fig.18

Fig.19

Fig.20

CONCLUSION:

The current study's findings aid in the identification of herbal formulations like *Trijataka*. , prismatic crystals, parenchymatous cell, fiber, epidermal cells, acicular crystal, starch grains, sclerenchyma of testa these structures are indicating presence of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton) .Starch grain, pitted vessel, phloem fiber, phloem parenchyma, parenchyma containing small acicular raphides, scleroids these structures are indicating presence of *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl). Fiber, pearl gland, thick-walled cell of upper epidermis, vessel, schizogenous mucilaginous canal, glandular trichomes, non-glandular trichomes these structures are indicating presence of *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.)

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